
PRIMA INSTRUMENT PERFORMANCE ART AND PRIMA RUBOB MUSICAL INSTRUMENTS.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7800161>

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Abstract.

This article provides information about the history of the creation and use of the Prima rubob musical instrument.

Key words.

Prima instrument performance art, prima rubob, music, art, culture, knowledge.

After the independence of our country, in order to reform the education system of music and art, to fundamentally update its content and essence, to provide it with modern technologies and tools, it was raised to the level of our state policy. issues of development of science, health care, culture and art, sports, ensuring that our young people have deep knowledge, mastering foreign languages and modern information and communication technologies will remain our priority." The art of music plays an important role in human life. In music, the subtle experiences of the human heart, sorrows and joys, ideas, thoughts are reflected by means of a specific rhythm and harmonious melody. The land we live in, nature surrounding us, various processes and situations in our life cause the birth of music. It is these situations and the processes that we perceive, the feelings that we feel turn into music and enter our lives again and again, helping us to enjoy life. More precisely, music is able to change a person's attitude to life, to give it a positive color and variety, and it has the divine power of imparting spiritual strength and elation to the human soul. Systematic improvement of Uzbek musical instruments has begun. In 1940, a group of music masters led by professor A.I. Petrosyans, an artist who served in Uzbekistan in the experimental laboratory at the Research Institute of Art Studies - Masters Usman Zufarov, V.A. Romonchenko, S.Y. Didenko, A.A. Kekhvoyans, X. Relying on the positive research and experience of Muhiddinov, N. Ryukhin, A. Abdug'afforov, B.B. Andreyev, many instruments such as dutor, tanbur are reconstructed, prima (small) rubobi is created. allows you to perform samples of his creations. The traditional Kashkar rubob bowl is carved from mulberry wood, while the newly created rubob bowl is made by joining

wooden ribs. Rubob prima bowl is also made of wooden plates, and the handle is made of apricot tree wood. The bowl is covered with fish skin. Four hooks are placed at the base of the bowl to hold the strings of the instrument. At the junction of the bowl and the handle, on both sides of the handle, there is a horn-shaped ear, which serves as a unique decoration. The strings are worn on mechanical ears fixed on the head of the rubab, and are transferred to the shaytan kharak at the head of the instrument and the kharak ("Kharrak" - a device that holds the string of the instrument) located on the fish skin covered in the cup. Shaitan harrak and harrak on the skin ensure the location of the strings at a certain height on the handle. Kharak should not be made of soft wood, on the contrary, it should be hard and of good quality. Because the speaker has a great influence on the sound quality. Rubob prima handle is divided by 24 metal plates, the mutual distance between them is called curtain. The frets are numbered from the head of the note to the bowl. 2, 5, 7, 10, 12, 14 frets have unique plastic or mother-of-pearl decorations of various shapes, which help in determining the location of notes on the staff. the location of the harrak is important when setting it up. In this case, the strings are pressed on the 12 frets of the instrument handle and the string sounds in octave intervals. If the open narrow octave sounds higher than the octave interval, then it is advisable to start tuning the instrument. Because the fish skin covering the bowl of the rubob prima instrument is very sensitive to air temperature, which causes the tone to change. So, at first, the second string is tuned to the LYA sound of the tuning fork or piano. Then the first string is tuned to MI, the third to RE, and the fourth to SOL. The sound of the instrument is checked by pressing the fifth and seventh frets and listening to see if the strings are tuned in an octave interval. Also, the quality of the strings is very important in tuning the instrument. Poor quality strings quickly become unusable, and the rubob prima instrument is out of tune in the curtains. In such cases, timely attention is required as strings. Today, the rubob prima instrument has a strong place in the performance practice. Among the new musical instruments, the prima rubob was first tested in the educational orchestra of the Music Academy in Tashkent under the leadership of A.I. Petrosyans. At that time, the orchestra of Uzbek folk instruments of the State Philharmonic of Uzbekistan served as a real laboratory in this regard. Thus, the improved Uzbek folk instruments, including the prima rubob, took a worthy place in the new type of orchestra of the State Philharmonic of Uzbekistan. In 1943, a unique experience in the improvement and reconstruction of folk instruments The musical orchestra of the Uzbekistan Philharmonic included 45 performers. 5 independent groups of

reconstructed instruments were formed in the orchestra. Among them, the group of stringed nakhun (mizrobli) instruments, including rubob-primas I, II, Kashgar rubob I, II, Afghan rubob I, II, dutor, bass and contrabass, gained leading and important importance. Rubob prima is a high-register instrument that has a range that allows you to play from the low octave of the violin to the 4th octave of E. In the orchestra of Uzbek folk choirs, rubob prima has a special importance and takes the leading place. Rubob prima folk instruments significantly increase the performance, skill, and sound of the group of mizrob and string instruments in the orchestra. Due to its great artistic and performance capabilities, rubob prima can perform classical examples of world music, works of well-known composers, Uzbek folk tunes, complex large works created by Uzbek composers with high skill. Compared to other instruments such as Kashgar rubob, Afghan rubob, dutor, the position of the rubob prima instrument is somewhat more important.

Because the playing range of the rubob prima instrument is large, all the strings are made of metals, and their adjustment according to the interval of a fifth makes it possible to play from string to string in any part of the instrument handle. This requires the student and any musician to master the positions, the ways of changing them, and the skills of putting the correct application. Such skills help the performer to master the arrangement of notes on the strings, read notes and develop performance skills. Up to our time, the rubob prima instrument has been highly valued by Andijan musicians Kozimjon Nizomiddinov, Abdumalik Madrahimov dynasty and their students. skillfully made. The musical instruments made by them serve the development of performing arts of Uzbekistan.

Conclusion:

In all regions of our country, children's music and art schools, music and art colleges, lyceums, and conservatories train specialists in this instrument. Today, in the laboratory of musical instruments, which continues its activity at the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan, this tune is made and delivered to specialists by such masters as B. Inoyatov, A. Islamov, H. Rakhmatov.

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